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Abstract

The main objective of the European funded project MICORE (Morphological Impacts and COastal Hazards induced by Extreme storm events) is to develop and demonstrate on-line tools for reliable predictions of the morphological impact of marine storm events in support of civil protection mitigation strategies. The project specifically aims at contributing to the development of a probabilistic mapping of the morphological impact of marine storms and to the production of Early Warning Systems to support long-term disaster reduction. The project is organized in 7 so-called Work Packages, one of which is WP5 – Early warning system development. The main goal of this work package is to demonstrate the capabilities of on-line early warning systems. WP5 includes 4 deliverables, from which D5.1 - GIS based hazard maps - is presented in this report. Based on the results presented in D5.1 it can be concluded that in general the combination of the calibrated XBeach model and GIS tools allowed the production of hazard maps for different storm impact indicators. For some areas, e.g. Praia de Faro in Portugal an alternative approach was needed and for other areas (e.g. France and Spain) only the hydrodynamic output of the model could be used. The presented hazard maps provide a valuable alternative (coastal safety) for existing coastal vulnerability maps on the one hand and on the other hand introduce information for several new coastal hazards related to coastal recreation. The GIS based hazard maps show that most of the test sites are highly vulnerable even for storm with low RP, i.e. 1/1 year (e.g. Italy) to moderate RP, i.e. 1/10 years (e.g. Portugal, Spain, Belgium, Poland and Bulgaria).

Disclaimer

The European funded project MICORE (Morphological Impacts and COastal Hazards induced by Extreme storm events), which main objective is to develop and demonstrate on-line tools for reliable predictions of the morphological impact of marine storm events in support of civil protection mitigation strategies and signed under grant agreement 2002798 follows the description of work (DoW) issued on May 2nd 2011.

In accordance with this Description of Work and the deliverable list presented in the DoW in Table 1.7 (pg. 38) the Deliverable D5.1, which is presented in this report, is of restricted dissemination level. Following the definition in the DoW, D5.1 is therefore restricted to a group specified by the consortium, including the Commission Services.

The content of this report therefore is of use of the Consortium and the Commission Services only and no parts may be disclosed to third parties without the written consent of all authors.

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10. GIS HAZARD MAPS – BULGARIA

This paragraph presents the GIS based hazard maps that are set-up for the project area in the Bulgaria. The GIS based hazard maps have been prepared by the Institute of Oceanology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.

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10.1 INTRODUCTION

The study area is located within the western Black Sea coast, and stretches from cape Paletsa to cape Cherni Nos (Figure 10-1). The area comprises the longest and the largest sandy beach along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, with well-developed dunes and two rivers mouths, those of the rivers Kamchia and Fandakliyska. In the central sector of the site, near the mouth of Fandakliyska river there is a scientific pier built perpendicularly to the shore. It is a 250 m-long permeable construction, as water depth at its far end reaches about 4.5 m. The beach is open to waves of the eastern half. Beach and dune morphology within the study area is presented by two types of cross-shore beach profiles – northern type with dunes and average beach slope of 8/100 and southern type which is dune-less and bi-sloped with bottom slopes of 1/100 landward end and 10/100 in the shoreward profile end (Figure 10-1).

Figure 10-1: Study site location. Deployment of measuring equipment is indicated as follows: $\diamond$ - position of the meteorological station and radar sea level gauge; $\blacksquare$ - ADCP location. Topobathymetric profiles are drawn with straight black lines. Typical cross-shore profiles are shown: Profile 3 in the northern part is uni-sloped with dune crest with elevation of 4.0 m and Profile 8 in the southern part is bi-sloped.

Large seasonal variability is the most remarkable feature of the wind and wave climate. The winter storms are much more frequent than those of summer. In the western Black Sea the most common are north-eastern and eastern winds. Having the largest fetch, they trigger the most severe storms. The north-eastern winds prevail in the northern and middle sections of the western shelf zone, while the impact of eastern winds increases southward. Generally, the south-eastern winds are less significant in terms of storm intensity but are still relevant for the northern shelf in particular (Valchev et al., 2008). Following the wind patterns waves propagate most frequently from east, northeast and southeast. The waves from other directions are less important in terms of both probability of occurrence and wave height. In the case of severe storms the wind gust can reach up to 35-40 m/s and maximum significant wave height – 8 m (at depths of about 30 m).

The coastal stretch for which hazard maps are produced is 1.2 km long. Three different typical beach profiles can be observed in northern middle and southern part of the study site.

Several approaches and related thresholds have been recently used to define storm for the area of interest. Valchev and Trifonova (2009) utilizing results of wave hindcast for western Black sea shelf, performed wave climate clustering and proposed a combined threshold, hereafter named initial wave threshold. The threshold takes into account wave conditions, in terms of H_s , T_m and θ_m causing intense sediment transport, that is sheet flow. The threshold discriminates between wave regimes capable of triggering morphological response and those which do not affect coastal morphology considerably. Valchev and Trifonova (2009) have shown that marked morphological changes could be produced only in 20% of all wave events. Following the above mentioned approach the available model wave data were threshold leveled to differentiate the events that fall within that particular cluster. Trifonova et al. (in press) considered wave energy as reference quantity for wave forcing which encompasses both intensity and duration of a given wave event. Thus, a storm threshold level of $0.15 \times 10^6 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ was introduced.

GIS based hazard maps are one of the main tools supporting the strategic actions to cope with social dimension of marine related hazards. They refer to storm events of given return periods (RP). Various return periods are considered in coastal engineering and management practice in Bulgaria. RP of 20 and 50 years are most frequently used for different classes of security of coastal structures. On the other hand, RP of 100 years is often referred to as relevant for assessment of extreme conditions. In addition to above mentioned ones, RP of 5 years is also considered as it refers to the extent of hazard which is rather frequently encountered in coastal management practice. In summary, return periods of 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years were employed for this study.

10.2 METHODOLOGY

10.2.1 MODELLING FRAMEWORK FOR THE SITE

10.2.1.1 Boundary conditions for storms of relevant return periods

As mentioned above, hazard maps are created for marine storms of different return periods. Prototype storm concept is adopted in order to recreate storm development and decay behaviour. It is based on existing experience in wave hind-casting (Valchev et al., 2008 and 2009) and on the information of historical storms gathered within WP1 (e.g. Valchev et al. 2009; Trifonova et al., 2010).

In addition, bi-variate extreme value analysis of wave height and storm surge level is performed in order to obtain storm characteristics in the phase of its maximum development (unpublished results). Extreme value methods are powerful statistical methods for drawing inference about the extremes of a process, using only data on relatively extreme values of the process. Extreme value methods are usually utilized for the purpose of extrapolation to levels more extreme than those which have been observed. The statistical methodology is motivated by a well-established mathematical theory (Extreme Value Theory), which relies on the assumption, that the limiting models suggested by the asymptotic theory continue to hold at finite but extreme levels (e.g. in Coles, 2001).

Extreme offshore wave heights are often strongly dependent on high sea levels. The observed water level is the sum of a deterministic astronomical tidal component and a stochastic meteorologically induced component, the surge. Dependence between surges and waves is expected, since both are related to local weather conditions (Hawkes et al., 2002). Strong dependence is likely in particular at extreme levels when meteorological systems, which generate extreme surges, also cause strong long-fetch onshore winds. Therefore, a bi-variate extreme value model is used to produce estimates of joint probabilities of extreme wave heights and storm surges for different return periods. Considering wave period extremes, a conditional distribution on extreme wave height is used. As a result of extreme value analysis following combined water level - wave height boundary conditions were used for considered return periods (Table 10-1).

Table 10-1: Boundary conditions for return periods (RP) of 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years; H_s stands for significant wave height, SSH for storm surge height and T_m for mean wave period.

RP [years]	H_s [m]	SSH [m]	T_m [s]	Duration [h]
5	5.57	0.50	7.89	86
10	5.92	0.65	8.2	89
20	6.18	0.66	8.47	91
50	6.47	0.73	8.87	93
100	6.67	0.79	9.08	95

10.2.1.2 Modelling behind hazard maps

For creation of the hazard maps morphological modelling of the prototype storms with return periods of 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years was performed by means of XBeach and IO-BAS MM models calibrated and validated for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi study site within WP4.

XBeach simulations of the prototype storms were performed on a modelling grid set in accordance with field measurements taken within WP3. The bathymetry in use was surveyed in March 2010, while the detailed topography was measured in March 2011. The span of the variable grid is 1400 x 1200 m and consists of 194 cells in cross-shore and 110 cells in long-shore direction (Figure 10-2). The same grid was used for 2D simulations which results were applied for validation of the GIS based hazard maps (Deliverable D5.2).

Figure 10-2: Modelling grid for Kamchia – Shkorpilovtsi study site. The calculation cells are denoted by small black dots, while the representative beach profiles are highlighted in red.

The whole study area was divided into three sections: northern (Section 1), middle (Section 2) and southern (Section 3) that correspond to spatial variations of beach morpho-metrics. One representative cross-shore profile was selected for each section. For construction of hazard maps 1D XBeach simulations were performed on the three selected profiles presented in Figure 10-3. The morphological feedback loop was included in all XBeach simulations.

Figure 10-3: Representative cross-shore profiles for Sections 1, 2 and 3 for Kamchia – Shkorpilovtci study site. Dashed lines show position of beach rear line, moveable property and non-moveable property along the profiles.

10.2.2 GIS hazard map methodology

10.2.2.1 Overall framework

In the frame of MICORE WP5 an early warning system prototype was designed and tested. It is based on a chain of hydro- and morphological models, as their output is translated into several storm impact indicators (SII) described in a frame of reference (Table 10-2). These indicators are the main instruments for evaluation of the storm impact at qualitative and quantitative level and eventually issue a number of warnings and undertake certain mitigation actions related to them. By means of the storm impact indicators the predicted state of physical properties considered hazardous is converted into a meaningful message to those threatened by them. In general, the focus is on hazards that can affect adversely human life, reduce the recreational beach capacity and damage property and infrastructure situated on or behind the beach. These are high water level in combination with dangerous currents, beach erosion and flooding, respectively.

10.2.2.2 Key physical parameters behind SIIs

Three key physical parameters chosen from the morphological modelling output are considered to be indicative for the degree of storm impact on the beach. These are:

- *Height-velocity* that accounts for possible dangerous conditions on the recreational beach strip and more specifically near the shoreline;
- *Maximum beach face retreat* that accounts for loss of recreational area due to coastal erosion;
- *Maximum wave run-up* that accounts for level of flooding.

In general, we are interested in that location along the profile at which the benchmark desired state was broken. This means that from this particular point onshore conditions are regarded as “safe” and offshore ones – as “unsafe”. It should be mentioned that conditions at depths greater than 1.0 m are always considered “unsafe”, hence, precaution and/or special measures should be proposed for people that might happened to be at such or even larger depths. This might be a topic of another SII in the future, e.g. swimmers safety.

Height-velocity (hv) product

Loss of human stability in flood flows and consequent drowning are considered to be a high personal hazard. Although the concept of high flood as a hazard for property damage and loss to human life has evolved during the 1970s and 1980s, the first study on loss of human stability in flood flows was found to be made by Abt et al. (1989). They conducted a series of experiments with rigid body monoliths and human subjects to identify the velocity and depth (height) of the flood flow at which an adult human could not stand or manoeuvre and eventually lose their stability. They proposed limits for human stability in flowing waters in the form of a critical height-velocity (hv) product as a function of weight and height of the subjects, which for standing mode varies in the interval 0.6-2 m²/s. Since then other authors have carried out similar experiments and proposed a number of theoretical models for human stability in high flows (Suetsugi, 1998; Karvonen et al. 2000; Lind et al., 2004; Jonkman & Penning-Rowell, 2008), but overall these studies show no significant difference from the results obtained by Abt et al. (1989).

Thus, in our study we adopt a height-velocity product of $0.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ as a lower limit of human stability in the swash zone during (major) storm/surge events.

Maximum beach face retreat

Maximum beach face retreat is associated with erosion, which is determined as a result of comparison of initial and final profiles in horizontal plain for points of equal elevation (Figure 10-4.)

Figure 10-4: Principal scheme for determination of maximum erosion.

Profile landward shifting indicates reduction of the beach area. Shore-line retreat in some cases is significantly less than the retreat at higher elevations. Therefore, the proposed methodology envisages selection of maximum retreat among all elevations in range.

Wave run-up

Flood extent refers to wave run-up along the beach profile on the beach (Roelvink et al., 2009; Trifonova, 2007). This SII accounting for safety of property and infrastructure is determined using the position of the maximum wave run-up calculated for the forecast period that denotes the last wet point before the shore.

10.2.2.3 Storm Impact Indicators

The first and the second SIIs deal with recreational area of the beach comprising the dry part of the initial profile. Human safety is the principal issue of the first SII “Evacuation procedure”. The boundary between “safe” and “unsafe” beach area is marked by a point along the profile at which $hv \geq 0.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (critical height-velocity). Evidently, this SII marks presence of rather high waters on beach accompanied by dangerous currents that reduces the corridor for safe utilization and may result in evacuation of people out of the hazardous zones and/or locations.

The second SII (Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity) has to do with human safety as well but primarily refers to the capacity of the beach to accommodate sufficient number of people, i.e. deals with its recreational function. This is relevant not only during the touristic season but also during the storm season since the prediction of erosion rate and related warnings can contribute to more effective response to consequences having in mind beach ability to recover.

The third SII (Coastal safety: property and infrastructure) deals with the hazard of flooding and subsequent damage or loss of property (moveable and non-moveable) and infrastructure located on and/or behind the recreational beach area. Therefore, it refers to the entire dry part of the initial profile. Flood extent is determined by the maximum wave run-up for a given surge and wave set-up level. As moveable we refer to property like parasols, deck-chairs, bar and restaurant equipment etc., and as non-moveable to temporal buildings on the beach, houses, etc. Infrastructure are mainly roads, bridges but also electric and water supply that could be partially / completely damaged or to malfunction as a result of the storm impact. Location of property and infrastructure at the study site is shown in Figure 10-5. For each coastal section referent position of moveable and non-moveable property is marked out.

Figure 10-5: Location of property and infrastructure at the study site.

All SIIs give notion about the safe corridor within the dry part of the computational profile that could be safely used for everyday recreation purposes and particularly during unfavourable or hazardous weather conditions such as those called forth by marine storms. Detailed frame of reference for each SII is given in the Table 10-2.

Table 10-2: Frame of reference for proposed storm impact indicators (SII) for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi beach (Bulgaria).

Storm Impact Indicator (SII)	Strategic Objective	Operational Objective	QSC	Benchmarking Desired State	Benchmarking Current State	Intervention Procedure	Evaluation Procedure
Evacuation Preparation (Evacuation)	Guarantee minimum threat to human lives in coastal areas during (major) storms.	Minimize the number of people in hazard zones.	Space-time maps of areas that are "safe" or "unsafe".	There should be no people in the hazardous coastal area. Threshold level is defined by height/velocity (h_v), which is the water depth [m] times the current speed [m/s]. Thus, "unsafe" is a location in the swash zone where $h_v > 0.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.	Hazard maps update in combination with recreational areas /facilities.	1. Flagging of hazardous conditions and locations; 2. Prevent beach access (e.g. road closure, mass media reports); 3. Evacuation of people from the area: vertical and horizontal	Check the number of people left exposed to risk during (major) storms.
Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity (Beach)	Guarantee reliable estimate of recreational capacity (sufficiently wide beach).	Monitoring of the impact of coastal flooding and beach / dune erosion.	Space-time maps of beach width.	Sufficiently wide dry beach: beach width > 50% of long-term beach width and average comfort level of 8m ² .	Compute beach capacity in regard to erosion front position and determination of number of people that can use the beach.	1. Daily estimate of the available space on the beach; 2. Inform interested parties .	Check predicted beach status against major post-storm ones.
Coastal safety: property and infrastructure (Property)	Guarantee minimum loss of property and safety of infrastructure.	Minimize the risk of property losses and damages on infrastructure.	Updated space-time maps of flood advance in regard to property location.	Max Wave run-up position lower than property position.	Maps of property overlaid by maps of flood advance .	1. Moveable property to be moved away to a safe location; 2. Measures to be taken for rendering property safe (e.g. turn off power supply, etc.); 3. Closure of roads if wave run-up exceeded a pre-define threshold levels.	Inspect the infrastructure integrity and eventual loss of property.

10.2.3 Warning levels and thresholds

Variations of key physical parameters along the profiles enables introduction of three levels of warning related to each of the described SII: green, orange and red. Green refers to low level of hazard, orange – to medium level of hazard, while red – to high level of hazard. These levels correspond to different mitigation actions that must be undertaken by responsible parties.

Thresholds for each of the warning levels are set based on a few morpho-metric features of the beach whose spatial variations were defined according to the field surveys performed within WP3. Thus, for each of the three representative profiles were determined: dry beach width (distance between shoreline and beach rear-line), seasonal shoreline position and seasonal rear-line position.

Then, hazard thresholds were projected along the profiles by means of zoning, as each zone corresponds to a given level of warning (Figure 10-6). Hence, different warning will be issued depending on the zone in which the benchmark desired state for each SII would be broken. For SII1 the thresholds between the warning levels are summarized in Table 10-3, while profile zoning is depicted in Figure 10-6. The percentage of the dry beach width varies slightly from section to section depending on the differences in beach width and profile slopes.

In order to issue a warning for this SII we check the position of the critical height-velocity ($0.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) along the profile, as the relevant warning level is determined depending on the zone within which the critical hv falls into.

Table 10-3: Warning levels' thresholds in percentage of dry beach width (distance between shoreline and beach rear-line).

Warning levels	Section 1 (Northern)	Section 2 (Middle)	Section 3 (Southern)
Green	Less than 20	Less than 15	Less than 20
Orange	Between 20 and 50	Between 15 and 40	Between 20 and 45
Red	More than 50	More than 40	More than 45

Figure 10-6: Visualization of the warning levels for SII 1 “Evacuation preparation” for a representative profile within Section 1 for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtci study site. Dashed lines show positions of beach rear line, moveable property and non-moveable property along the profile. The black pointer shows location where hv product reached or exceeded the critical height-velocity value. Results are based on XBeach modelling of the storm of March 2011.

For the second SII dealing with beach recreational capacity the warning levels’ thresholds are given according to percentage of the eroded beach width (Table 10-4). For this SII the threshold values do not differ from section to section. Thus, if maximum beach face retreat exceeds 20% of the dry beach-width the warning issued would be orange, while if it exceeds 50% warning turns to red. The location of warning levels is depicted in Figure 10-7.

Figure 10-7: Visualization of the warning levels for SII 2 “Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity” for a representative profile within Section 1 for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtci study site. Dashed lines show positions of beach rear line, moveable property and non-moveable property along the profile. The black pointer shows position of the maximum displacement of the beach face. Results are based on XBeach modelling of the storm of March 2011.

For the third SII warning levels' thresholds are determined according to respective positions of property (moveable and non-moveable) and flood extent along the profile. Thus, if the maximum wave run-up reaches a position at distance one computational cell ahead of the location of moveable property the warning is set to orange, while it is one computational cell ahead of the location of non-moveable property warning turns to red. SII2 and SII3 thresholds are summarized in Table 10-4.

Table 10-4: Warning levels' thresholds for SII 2 and SII3.

Warning levels	SII2 Beach recreational capacity	SII3 Property and Infrastructure
Green	Less than 20	Moveable property not flooded
Orange	Between 20 and 50	Non-moveable property not flooded
Red	More than 50%	Non-movable property flooded

In Figure 10-8 the position in which every key physical parameter reaches the prescribed critical value is marked by a pointer that on its turn defines the warning level.

Figure 10-8: Visualization of the warning levels for SII 3 "Coastal safety: property and infrastructure" for a representative profile within Section 1 for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi study site. Dashed lines show positions of beach rear line, moveable property and non-moveable property along the profile. The black pointer shows position of the maximum wave run-up. Results are based on XBeach modelling of the spring storm of March 2011.

10.3 RESULTS OF THE GIS BASED HAZARD MAPS

The hazard maps for the proposed SIIs are prepared following the same concept as the output from EWS (D5.3). The warning levels for each of the SIIs were determined using the profiles chosen from each of the three sections on Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi study site (Fig. 2).

The maps were compiled for storm events with RP of 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years, but since levels of warning for extreme storms with RP of 20, 50 and 100 years turned out to be equivalent in terms of methodology in use, herein we present a hazard map only for RP of 100 years. More details are given in Annex A.

10.3.1 GIS based hazard map for the 1/5 years storm event

The hazard map for the 1/5 years storm event is illustrated on Figure 10-9. For this return period the XBeach model predicted the following hazards related to evacuation preparation and coastal safety of both beach and property.

Figure 10-9: Hazard map for RP of 5 years for Kamchia-Sjorkopilovtsi beach.

10.3.1.1 Evacuation preparation

The predicted warning level for the first SII is “medium hazard” for all beach sections for storms with RP of 5 years. This means that the position of the critical height-velocity along the representative profiles is estimated to be beyond ~ 20% of the beach width. In other words, hydrodynamic processes (high sea level and/or high current velocities) in the upper swash zone appear to be strong enough to cause a person to topple over and thus threatening their life.

The result clearly shows that SII1 is quite sensitive to variation of critical hv , because it is oriented towards safety of people on the beach during the active touristic season when no severe storms would be expected. At that time of the year, warnings could be used from safeguards, for example.

10.3.1.2 Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity

For section 1 the beach width along the chosen profile is 40 m and maximum beach face retreat is estimated to 30 m, as for section 3 where the beach width is 88 m the relevant retreat is 43 m, which means that for these sections the maximum retreat did not exceed the beach widths along the initial profiles. On the other hand, within section 2 the maximum beach face retreat exceeds beach width (42m) and reaches up to 65 m.

These results indicate that for sections 1 and 2 more than 50% of the beach was eroded, which gives a warning level "red". For section 3 the warning level is "Orange", although the calculated retreat is close to the higher threshold. The result might be a matter of erosion over-prediction; therefore, related warnings should be issued with certain precaution.

10.3.1.3 Coastal safety: property and infrastructure

For the third SII results show that flood extent does not reach either moveable or non-moveable property for section 1. In the central part (section 2) even for storm with RP of 5 years the flood extent is estimated to be behind the non-moveable property. In southern part (section 3) the flood extent is calculated to reach the area between moveable and non-moveable property (Fig. 3).

Only in section 1 moveable property is located far behind the dune crest. In section 2 moveable property locations coincides with beach rear line, and in section 3 it is located within the recreational area of the beach. Thus, storm flooding reaches moveable and even non-moveable property in section 2 during these events, which translates into warning level "green" indicating low hazard for section 1, "red" indicating high hazard for section 2 and "orange" for section 3. Conditions described for sections 2 and 3 imply that whole recreational area of the beach is subjected to inundation and measures of safety should be taken with regard to properties under consideration.

10.3.2 GIS based hazard map for the 1/10 years storm event

The hazard map for the 1/10 years storm event is illustrated in Figure 10-10. For this return period the XBeach model predicted the following hazards related to evacuation preparation and coastal safety of both beach and property.

Figure 10-10: Hazard map for the 1/10 years storm event for Kamchia-Sjtkorpilovtsi beach.

10.3.2.1 Evacuation preparation

Results show that the predicted warning level for the first SII is indicating again “high hazard” for all beach sections. Position of the critical height-velocity along the representative profiles for all sections is estimated to be beyond the beach rear line, as the distance between shoreline position and the position of the critical height-velocity exceeds the beach width more than two to three times.

10.3.2.2 Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity

For section 1 the maximum beach face retreat is estimated to be 32 m, which means that the maximum retreat did not exceed the beach width along the initial profile. On the other hand, within sections 2 and 3 the maximum beach face retreat exceeds beach width (42 m and 68 m respectively) and reaches up to 78 m and 73 m, respectively. These results indicate that for all sections for these events already more than 50% of the beach was eroded, which again gives a warning level “red” indicating high hazard.

10.3.2.3 Coastal safety: property and infrastructure

The obtained results show that only for the northern part of the study site the predicted flood extent reaches up to the moveable property giving “orange” level of warning (medium hazard). In the other two sections (2 and 3) the flooding extends behind the non-moveable property, which gives a warning level “red” indicating high hazard.

10.3.3 GIS hazard maps for the 1/100 years storm event

The hazard map for the 1/100 years storm event is illustrated on Figure 10-11. For this return period the XBeach model predicted the following hazards related to evacuation preparation and coastal safety of both beach and property.

Figure 10-11: GIS hazard map for the 1/100 years storm event for Kamchia-Sjtkorpilovtsi beach.

10.3.3.1 Evacuation preparation

Results show the predicted warning level for the first SII is indicating “high hazard” for all beach sections. Position of the critical height-velocity along the representative profiles for all sections is also estimated to be beyond the beach rear line, as in this case the distance between shoreline position and the position of the critical height-velocity exceeds the beach width more than three to five times.

10.3.3.2 Coastal safety: beach recreational capacity

As it was mentioned previously, the beach width along the initial profiles for sections 1, 2 and 3 are 40 m, 42 m and 88 m, respectively. Herein, the maximum beach face retreat is estimated to reach distances of 73 m, 103 m, and 83 m landward advancing beyond the beach rear line, thus exceeding the beach width in some cases with more than two times. This means that for such extreme storms the recreational part of the beach would be subjected to severe erosion and even its recovery capabilities could be compromised. The level of warning indicates “high hazard”.

10.3.3.3 Coastal safety: property and infrastructure

Results show that the estimated flooding extends behind the benchmarking position of non-moveable property for the entire study area, which gives a warning level “red” indicating high hazard for all sections. These conditions imply that whole recreational area of Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi beach is subjected to inundation and measures of safety should be taken with regard to properties under consideration.

10.4 CONCLUSIONS

Following the methodology of the Early Warning System (EWS) prototype hazard maps were compiled based on the predictions of XBeach model simulations and storm impact indicators (SII) developed for Kamchia-Shkorpilovtsi beach area. The proposed SII concern hazard to human life, as well as to coastal safety in the scope of beach recreational capacity, property and infrastructure.

Analysis of the compiled maps allows concluding that different sections of the beach are vulnerable to flooding and erosion hazard to different degree. Thus, for similar hydrodynamic conditions different flood extents could be predicted for adjacent beach sections, which is due to the local morpho-metric patterns. In the same manner, similar erosion rates could be translated into different warning levels if applied to sections with different beach width. These considerations could lead us to a conclusion that similar hydro- and morphodynamic manifestations could be referred to different warning levels depending on the morphological characteristics of a given beach area that in general proves the adequacy of the selected SII. However, in the same time results imply that one of the ways to improve the Early Warning System should concern verification of warning thresholds and GIS hazard maps as a whole. Thus far, the adopted methodology shows that even for low return periods of 5 and 10 years the middle and the southern parts of the study site are subjected to high levels of hazard for all impact indicators. The elaborated hazard maps should grant access to all interested in the subject end-user in order to increase their awareness to extreme storm phenomena.

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Annex A GIS based hazard maps

A.8 Hazard maps Bulgaria

